

Review

Menopause and Traditional Chinese Medicine: Evidence, Syndromic Perspectives, and a Self-Care Protocol Proposal.

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Abstract

Background: Menopause is a physiological transition characterised by ovarian failure and hypoestrogenism, leading to multisystemic symptoms that affect women's physical, psychological, and social well-being. Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) provides a holistic framework for understanding this period through concepts such as *Yin–Yang* imbalance, *Jing* (essence) depletion, and *Zang-Fu* disharmonies. While Western medicine emphasises hormonal therapy and lifestyle modification, TCM offers complementary strategies aimed at systemic energetic regulation.

Objective: To analyse menopausal care from the perspective of TCM, compare Eastern and Western therapeutic paradigms, identify predominant TCM syndromes, review available evidence on TCM interventions, and present a structured self-care protocol for climacteric women.

Methods: A narrative review of classical TCM theory, Western biomedical literature, and 14 experimental studies on acupuncture, *Qigong*, herbal medicine, auriculotherapy, moxibustion, and diet therapy. Additionally, a self-care protocol grounded in TCM theory was systematised based on established clinical principles.

Results: TCM conceptualises menopause as a decline in Kidney *Jing* and *Yin*, leading to disharmonies involving the Heart, Liver, Spleen, and key Extraordinary Meridians (*Chong*, *Ren*, *Du*). Reviewed studies showed that interventions such as *Qigong*, acupuncture (including ACE and laser), herbal formulas, and diet therapy significantly improved vasomotor symptoms, sleep, anxiety/depression, urogenital atrophy, metabolic parameters, and overall quality of life.

A TCM-based self-care protocol was developed, integrating several relevant exercises targeting the core climacteric disharmonies by reinforcing Kidney energy, nourishing *Yin*, regulating the Heart–Kidney axis, and restoring *Qi* (vital energy) flow, supporting symptom relief and self-management.

Conclusion: TCM offers a comprehensive and personalised approach to menopausal care, with evidence indicating effectiveness across vasomotor, psychological, urogenital, and metabolic domains. The proposed self-care protocol provides an accessible, low-risk tool for women to actively regulate symptoms and maintain energetic balance. Future research should include larger, standardised clinical trials and long-term follow-ups to validate TCM interventions and support their integration into evidence-based, integrative menopausal healthcare.

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1. Background

Menopause is a milestone in a woman's reproductive life and corresponds to a physiological stage following the spontaneous cessation of menstruation, characterised by approximately one year of absence of the menstrual period, during which the menstrual and ovulatory cycles cease. In other words, it marks the end of the female sexual phases, a period in which the definitive cessation of ovarian activity in the release of follicles occurs, and therefore, the female reproductive capacity¹. According to Duarte², this transition can be physiological or natural and will depend on the woman's individual natural biological process. This cessation commonly occurs around 51 years of age in European countries; however, age is not the only determining factor. There are others that can contribute to this process, such as genetic predisposition or lifestyle habits (tobacco consumption, diet, physical activity, or intense mental distress)³.

In this female condition, there is reproductive gland failure, as a reduction in oestrogen production occurs, stimulating the development of symptoms that influence the biological, physiological, and psychological aspects of her life⁴. Numerous authors cite these manifestations: amenorrhoea (absence of menstruation), vasomotor manifestations (hot flushes, sweating/diaphoresis, and headaches), depression, emotional, mood, and sleep changes, increased risk of myocardial infarction, vulvovaginal atrophy, urinary incontinence, recurrent urinary tract infections, changes in the elasticity, thickness, and resistance of the skin, increased risk of Alzheimer's and Cerebral Vascular Accident (CVA), concentration deficits and recent memory loss, reduced salivary flow, higher frequency of dental caries and tooth loss, weight gain, changes in the hairline, joint and bone pain, reduction in vaginal lubrication and libido. Psychological health is directly influenced, thus causing a strong impact on work, social, and conjugal life, and consequently, on her quality of life⁴⁻⁸.

Menopause is not an isolated event, but a specific point within the climacteric, the transition period between the reproductive and non-reproductive phases. Its classification varies according to aetiology and chronology, including iatrogenic types (induced by medical interventions), early (<40 years), and late (>53 years). The phase preceding it is called perimenopause, characterised by menstrual irregularity and endocrine changes, while the postmenopause encompasses the entire subsequent period.

From a therapeutic perspective, epidemiology is crucial: the age of menopause onset correlates directly with specific health risks for women. Early menopause is associated with higher overall and cardiovascular mortality due to the premature deprivation of oestrogen's cardioprotective effects, demanding an approach focused on the prevention of osteomuscular and cardiometabolic comorbidities. Conversely, late menopause, with prolonged hormonal exposure, raises the risk of hormone-dependent neoplasms (e.g., breast, endometrium), requiring specialised action in post-surgical rehabilitation and the management of sequelae such as lymphoedema^{2,9}.

Thus, therapeutic intervention should be initiated early, personalised, and based on the patient's individual risk profile, aiming to maintain functionality and quality of life throughout the entire climacteric spectrum. The care approach for these women must be personalised, involving the individualisation of clinical factors and biomarkers necessary to stratify risk, identifying the intervention that best suits each individual¹⁰.

Ultimately, it involves active and supportive listening to emphasise the pursuit of well-being for women during the climacteric. To achieve this, it is necessary to understand the complexity of this phase and its impact on their lives. It is the responsibility of healthcare professionals to support them through the grief of losing the capacity to conceive, or the fear of the unknown that lies ahead. It represents an opportunity to rethink life and accept that changes are natural facts in human evolution. Therapeutic assistance encompasses various practices, both in the Western and Eastern contexts¹¹.

Western Medicine employs both medicinal and non-medicinal therapies. The former primarily focuses on Hormone Replacement Therapy (HRT) and vitamin supplementa-

tion⁶ to treat menopausal symptoms. However, the non-medicinal approach includes nutritional guidance, advocating for a suitable diet combined with physical activity, and modification of habits, such as avoiding smoking and/or excessive alcohol consumption¹², stress management, and attention to interpersonal relationships¹³. In contrast, TCM offers complementary approaches such as acupuncture, herbal medicine, and changes in diet and lifestyle to rebalance the body's energy¹⁴.

In the East, health promotion also involves practicing breathing exercises, martial arts, or other therapeutic practices like *Yoga*, *Taijiquan*, *Qigong*, and meditation, which, besides enhancing physical fitness, contribute to the ascent of these women's mental and emotional balance¹¹.

This work was developed with the aim of verifying assistance in menopause through TCM, justified by the influence of menopause and the associated bodily and mental changes, which impair several contexts of the affected women's quality of life. The objectives of this research are: To conduct a literature review on menopause and its repercussions on the human body, to draw a parallel between the TCM and traditional perspectives, to differentiate existing treatments between Western and Eastern views of menopausal care, and to identify the main TCM treatment lines and their responses.

2. Menopause

Menopause is a biological process inherent to female ageing. The average life expectancy has increased in recent years, and consequently, mortality has decreased, a factor that contributes to the global ageing of the population, resulting in an increasingly large percentage of the female population being in the postmenopause phase. Currently, in general, women will live about one-third of their life in postmenopause¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

When referring to the term menopause, it is of utmost importance to respect the internationally pre-established definitions:

- Pre-menopause – encompasses the entire reproductive phase preceding Menopause¹⁸.
- Menopause – represents the date of the last menstruation, consequently, definitive ovarian failure. The clinical diagnosis is only confirmed retrospectively after 12 consecutive months of amenorrhoea, not resulting from another pathological or physiological cause.
- Perimenopause – includes the phase preceding menopause (the preamble of the endocrinological, biological, and clinical modifications of the proximity of menopause) and the first year after menopause¹⁸.
- Postmenopause – designates the period subsequent to the last menstruation^{18,19}.

The aetiology of menopause is neither consensual nor definitive, as it is a natural and inevitable biological process. In about 74% to 90% of cases, it is classified as idiopathic, being identified by a set of symptoms²⁰.

As of the present moment, there is no independent biological marker to determine this diagnosis, thus dispensing with the serial measurement of oestradiol or Follicle-Stimulating Hormone (FSH). The common age marker is between 45 and 55 years, mostly established genetically, but there are other attributes involved, such as external factors (lifestyle). Among these, smoking is the most notorious^{15,17}, as, in smoking women, menopause tends to occur two years earlier^{15,17,19}.

Besides smoking, there are other less explicit correlated factors: nulliparity, endometriosis, manifestation of autoimmune diseases, medication, surgical intervention, exposure to toxic chemicals, chemotherapy, pelvic radiation, epilepsy, and treatment for depression¹⁵.

There are also factors that can postpone the onset of menopause, such as obesity, multiparity, and alcoholism, being classified as late when its occurrence is evidenced after

53 years of age. Due to prolonged oestrogen exposure, increased attention is warranted for the risk of breast and endometrial cancer in these cases ^{15,21}.

Menopause is a natural process, but it can be artificially induced with the total and instant loss of hormonal production, as in cases of Iatrogenic Menopause, which is defined by the cessation of menstrual flow due to surgical intervention on the ovaries (with or without hysterectomy) or after iatrogenic ablation of ovarian function (chemotherapy or radiation) ¹⁸.

After characterising the different types of menopause, it is important to highlight that the progressive decline in ovarian function, associated with the inherent hormonal changes, is not limited to the reproductive scope. This process triggers a wide range of physiological and psychosocial repercussions that, in the short, medium, and long term, can compromise a woman's quality of life. The symptomatology is multisystemic, interfering with physical health, emotional balance, and the performance of daily activities, whether in the work, relational, or affective context ¹⁹.

The intensity, duration, and combination of symptoms vary significantly among women, reflecting a complex interaction between biological, psychological, social, and cultural factors. This heterogeneity shows that the clinical manifestations of menopause constitute an individualised phenomenon, whose understanding is essential for defining appropriate therapeutic strategies ².

2.1. Manifestations in the Short and Medium Term:

- The first changes include menstrual irregularities, such as changes in flow pattern and cycle duration, resulting from ovarian dysfunction and anovulation ²².
- Vasomotor symptoms (VMS), such as hot flushes and night sweats, are the most characteristic, affecting up to 75% of women, with pathophysiology related to the dysregulation of the hypothalamic thermoregulatory centre ²³.
- Sleep disturbances, such as insomnia and recurrent awakenings, are common and often associated with VMS ²⁴.
- Genitourinary Syndrome causes vaginal and urethral atrophy, dryness, urinary urgency, dyspareunia, and recurrent urinary tract infections ²⁵.
- Skin changes include skin thinning, loss of elasticity, hirsutism, and alopecia ²⁶.
- Psychological impacts, such as emotional lability, irritability, and depression, are frequent and multifactorial, intensified by physical symptoms and psychosocial factors ²⁷.

2.2. Clinical Manifestations in the Long Term

In the postmenopausal period, oestrogen deficiency triggers a series of physiopathological changes that substantially increase the risk of developing cardiovascular diseases and osteoporosis.

- The redistribution of body fat to the abdominal compartment promotes a state of chronic inflammation and thrombogenicity (capacity to induce blood clot formation), characterised by the elevation of inflammatory markers (TNF-alpha, IL-6, CRP) and reduced adiponectin levels, while the lipid profile becomes progressively atherogenic (capable of inducing/favouring the formation of fatty plaques that accumulate on artery walls), with increased low-density lipoproteins (LDL), triglycerides, and lipoprotein(a), and decreased cardioprotective subclasses of high-density lipoproteins (HDL) ²⁸.
- Endothelial dysfunction, resulting from reduced nitric oxide availability and increased oxidative stress, exacerbates arterial hypertension and insulin resistance, fundamental components of the metabolic syndrome, whose prevalence increases significantly during the menopausal transition ²⁹.
- The risk of cardiovascular events quadruples in the first decade after menopause, with arterial hypertension affecting approximately three-quarters of women in this

phase, often aggravated by greater sensitivity to sodium and hyperactivity of the Renin-Angiotensin-Aldosterone System (RAAS) (hormonal mechanism for regulating blood pressure and fluid and electrolyte balance in the body) ^{30,31}.

Concomitantly, oestrogen deficiency potentiates osteoclast activity, accelerating the rate of bone resorption and leading to an accelerated loss of Bone Mineral Density (BMD) of 2-3% per year during the first 3-4 years of postmenopause, subsequently stabilising to 1-1.5% per year ³². This process results in the deterioration of bone microarchitecture, increasing skeletal fragility and the risk of fragility fractures. Approximately 30% of women develop osteoporosis, with vertebral and hip fractures being particularly prevalent (the latter associated with a mortality of 5-20% in the first year after the fracture and permanent disability in 25% of cases) ³³. Bone loss is especially pronounced in Caucasian and Asian women, and the combination of low BMD with changes in dermal collagen composition may constitute an indirect marker of osteoporotic risk ³⁴.

The clinical manifestations of menopause, ranging from vasomotor symptoms and genitourinary changes to cardiometabolic and osteoarticular complications, reflect the complex pathophysiology of the climacteric. This transition period, marked by the progressive decline of ovarian function and the resulting state of hypoestrogenism, is not limited solely to the end of reproductive function ³⁵.

The climacteric involves not only hormonal changes but also transformations of a biological, psychological, and social nature, requiring an integrative approach that considers the interaction between endocrine, metabolic, emotional, and contextual factors ¹⁹. Understanding this phase as a continuous set of interconnected changes is essential for developing comprehensive therapeutic strategies that seek not only to alleviate symptoms but also to prevent long-term comorbidities and promote quality of life during this inevitable stage of female ageing.

2.3. The Climacteric and its Physiology

The climacteric constitutes the transition period between the reproductive and non-reproductive phases of a woman, characterised by the progressive decline of ovarian function and follicular exhaustion, resulting in sustained hypoestrogenism ³⁵. This phase encompasses a set of signs and symptoms, designated as the "climacteric syndrome", which include menstrual irregularities, vasomotor symptoms, mood swings, and sleep disturbances, among others, with a significant impact on the woman's biopsychosocial well-being. The climacteric is divided into three non-linear phases: pre-menopause, perimenopause, and postmenopause, with menopause (permanent cessation of menstruation, confirmed after 12 months of amenorrhoea) being its central event, occurring on average at 51 years of age ^{36,37}.

Physiologically, the process begins around 35-40 years of age with the accelerated depletion of ovarian follicles and hypothalamic-pituitary dysfunction ³⁸⁻⁴⁰. In perimenopause, the endocrine compensation by the elevation of FSH and LH levels attempts to maintain folliculogenesis, leading to anovulatory cycles, menstrual irregularities, and the appearance of symptoms such as hot flushes and sleep disturbances ^{41,42}. The Menopausal Transition (MT), as defined by the STRAW system, is divided into the early phase (>7 days variation in cycle duration) and the late phase (≥ 60 days amenorrhoea and/or $\text{FSH} \geq 40$ IU/L), culminating in menopause and subsequent entry into postmenopause, marked by permanent hypoestrogenism ^{36,43}.

Hormonal Characterisation

The endocrine changes of the climacteric result from the progressive depletion of the ovarian follicular reserve and the dysfunction of the remaining oocytes and granulosa cells. This dysfunction initially manifests as a decrease in Inhibin B (a glycoprotein hormone), produced by the ovarian granulosa cells, reducing the negative feedback on the pituitary gland and leading to the early elevation of FSH levels ^{37,44}. About six years before

menopause, the acceleration of follicular depletion intensifies the drop in Inhibin B and the elevation of FSH, triggering a compensatory follicular response with shortening of the follicular phase and transient maintenance of normal or elevated oestrogen levels – a state of transient hyperoestrogenaemia characteristic of the early phase of the menopausal transition^{36,43}.

The pronounced reduction in oestradiol production begins in the late phase of the menopausal transition, deepening up to one year after menopause and continuing gradually in subsequent years. The resulting hypoestrogenism is responsible for the typical climacteric symptomatology⁴⁵. In postmenopause, a state of hypergonadotrophic hypogonadism is established, with FSH levels 10-15 times higher and LH levels 3-5 times higher than in the reproductive period, associated with low oestradiol and undetectable Inhibin B³⁷. Oestrogen production then depends exclusively on the extragonadal aromatisation of androgens into oestrone⁴⁶.

In parallel, there is a 50% reduction in androstenedione levels and a 25% reduction in total testosterone, although ovarian secretion of testosterone persists due to the stimulation of the stroma by elevated LH. The decrease in Sex Hormone-Binding Globulin (SHBG) increases the bioavailability of testosterone, which may explain the development of hirsutism and virilising symptoms in some postmenopausal women⁴⁷.

3. Traditional Chinese Medicine and Western Medicine: A Parallel on Menopausal Care

Western Medicine approaches menopause as a biological milestone resulting from ovarian failure. This perspective emphasises the loss of fertility as the central axis, attributing a determining role to hormonal changes in clinical manifestations and a woman's quality of life^{35,48}.

In contrast, TCM interprets this transition as part of a natural movement of transformation of *Jing*, *Yin*, and *Yang*, in which the cessation of menstruation is not understood as a loss, but as a reorientation of *Qi* towards the cultivation of longevity, emotional balance, and spiritual strengthening^{49,50}.

A woman's vitality is understood by the fundamental principle of *Yin* and *Yang*, where *Yin* represents the feminine essence (receptivity, internalisation, and materiality) while *Yang* symbolises an active and transformative energy. The climacteric is interpreted as a period of accentuated *Yin* depletion, resulting in energetic disharmonies that manifest physically and psycho-emotionally. Symptoms such as hot flushes, night sweats, insomnia, and mucosal dryness are understood as direct expressions of this deficiency, while agitation, emotional instability, and the tendency towards depression reflect difficulties in finding a new axis of balance⁵¹.

These manifestations arise from specific disharmony patterns, involving fundamental Organs (*Zang*) according to the Theory of the Five Energetic Movements (*Wu Xing*).

- The Kidney (Water), the root of reproductive vital energy (*Jing*), is associated with hot flushes and menopausal symptoms when deficient.
- The Liver (Wood), responsible for storing blood and the free circulation of *Qi*, manifests through menstrual irregularities and mood changes.
- The Spleen-Pancreas (Earth), central to the formation of *Qi* and Blood, can lead to dysfunctional bleeding and fluid retention when compromised^{51,52}.

In addition to the Organs, TCM attributes a crucial role to the Extraordinary Meridians in integrating reproductive functions.

- The *Chong Mai* (Sea of Blood), associated with the Earth and Water elements, nourishes the uterus with *Xue* (Blood) and *Jing*.
- The *Ren Mai* (Vessel of Conception), linked to *Yin* and Water, regulates gestation.

- The *Du Mai* (Governing Vessel), related to *Yang* and Fire, sustains reproductive vital energy.
- The *Yin Qiao Mai* and *Yin Wei Mai* meridians, associated with Water and Earth, organise menstrual cycles and stabilise *Yin* energy⁵³.

The interaction between extraordinary meridians and associated Organs of the Five Elements is fundamental for understanding the aetiopathology of gynaecological disorders, as they function as energy reservoirs that connect reproductive functions to the body's natural cycles⁵³. The most common syndromic patterns in the climacteric – such as Kidney and Liver *Yin* Deficiency, Disharmony between Heart and Kidney, and Kidney and Spleen Yang Deficiency – require distinct therapeutic approaches to restore *Yin-Yang* balance and harmony between the Organs⁵⁴.

This holistic view, which integrates body, mind, and vital energy, contrasts with the biomedical approach focused on hormonal physiology, offering distinct possibilities for care and promotion of well-being for women in the non-reproductive phase.

3.1. Female Physiology

Female reproductive ageing is a continuous and programmed physiological process, characterised by the progressive decline of ovarian reserve. In TCM, this process is conceptualised in seven-year cycles, as described in the classic *Huang Di Nei Jing*. According to this perspective, menopause occurs around 49 years of age, an age at which the decline of the Ren Mai and Chong Mai meridians is observed, resulting in the cessation of menstruation and physical changes associated with ageing⁵⁵.

Curiously, this millenary prediction aligns with modern epidemiological observations indicating the mean ages of natural menopause around 51 years in Western populations^{56,57} and 50.7 years in Malaysian women⁵⁸, suggesting a universal and relatively constant biological basis for this developmental milestone.

From a pathophysiological point of view, menopause constitutes the clinical expression of ovarian follicular exhaustion. A woman has approximately 7 million primordial follicles during foetal life, a value that decreases to about 600,000 at birth, 300,000 at menarche, and only 10,000 at the transition to menopause⁵⁹. This gradual decline, which begins *in utero*, confirms the prolonged and inexorable nature of reproductive ageing.

This process is articulated with the concept of *Jing*, understood as an innate energetic-material substrate that governs growth, development, reproduction, and ageing. *Jing*, which notably expresses itself in follicular formation and maturation, is considered a finite, non-renewable resource. Its depletion is influenced by factors such as nutrition, sleep patterns, physical activity, stress, sexual behaviours, parity, and inter-gestational intervals⁵³. Thus, the preservation of *Jing* through healthy lifestyles since childhood is considered crucial for modulating the trajectory of reproductive ageing.

However, menopause is often medicalised and culturally stigmatised as a symbol of decline, generating anxiety and negative perceptions⁵¹. A more integrative approach, such as that proposed by Campiglia⁵¹, views this transition as a natural "eventide", a phase of transformation and potential renewal, whose experience varies significantly between individuals. Acceptance of this physiological transition, rather than its pathologisation, appears to be fundamental for promoting physical and psychological well-being during this period.

In summary, the study of female physiology benefits from an integrated view that combines the ancestral knowledge of TCM (with its intuitive description of life cycles and the importance of Essence) with the quantitative precision of modern biomedicine, which details follicular dynamics and the epidemiology of menopause. Recognising menopause as a natural and universal biological process and not as a disease allows for a more holistically informed and empowering approach to this fundamental phase of a woman's life.

3.2. The Domain of Yin

The *Yin* principle represents the material and structural basis of the organism, manifesting in body fluids, blood, organic matter, and temperature maintenance. In the context of female physiology, *Yin* prevails as the dominant force, conferring a denser and less active nature compared to masculine *Yang* energy. This *Yin* predominance explains the tendency towards recollection and lower tolerance to cold temperatures in the female sex⁶⁰.

The decline of *Yin* associated with reproductive ageing directly influences the symptomatology of the climacteric. As *Yin* diminishes, an energetic imbalance occurs that tends to manifest through a relative excess of *Yang*, making the woman more vulnerable to emotional fluctuations, irritability, and restlessness. This energy transition is mediated by the Uterus Meridian (Bao Mai), which establishes a functional connection between the Heart (Fire) and the Kidneys (Water). While Water governs the ancestral matrix (genetic heritage and phenotypic expression), Fire regulates the hormonal axes, particularly the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis^{61,62}.

As described in the Yellow Emperor's Classic, women reach a critical energy transformation at 49 years of age; the *Qi* undergoes transmutation without corresponding changes in *Xue*, a process that fundamentally depends on the Kidney energy⁶³. When this transition does not occur harmoniously, imbalances manifest through specific symptoms⁶⁴:

1. Heart (*Xin*) Changes: anxiety, irritability, insomnia, fatigue, depression, reduced libido, and impaired memory.
2. Kidney (*Shèn*) Changes: hot flushes, night sweats, palpitations, headaches, and dizziness.
3. Extraordinary Meridian Imbalances: dyspareunia, vulvar pruritus, irregular bleeding, fibroids, and dysfunctional uterine haemorrhages.
4. Liver (*Gan*) and Dai Mai Changes: pain and mammary dysplasia.
5. Spleen-Pancreas (*Pi*) and Liver (*Gan*) Deficiency: joint pain, muscle pain, and osteoporosis.
6. Compromised Tissue Nutrition: atrophy and cutaneous dryness.

The primary causes of these disharmonies include: (1) aggression to *Qi* and *Xue*, (2) depletion of the Essential *Jing*, and (3) chronic processes of energy degradation that affect the Kidney, Liver, Spleen-Pancreas, and Heart⁶⁰.

The fundamental therapeutic principle is based on strengthening the *Jin Ye* (body fluids), tonifying the *Jing*, and reinforcing Kidney energy, aiming to restore the balance between *Yin* and *Yang* during this natural physiological transition⁶².

3.3. Difference Existing Between Care Perspectives

In the context of the different care perspectives on the climacteric, contemporary Western medicine predominantly emphasises evidence-based interventions, while the Eastern perspective integrates traditional holistic approaches. As Duarte² highlights, this dichotomy reflects distinct paradigms for understanding the physiological transformations inherent to this phase of a woman's life.

Western Perspective

Physical Activity

The contemporary Western approach prioritises physical activity as a fundamental pillar for healthy ageing. Regular practice is proven to improve muscle elasticity, blood circulation, and joint mobility, constituting determining factors for the comprehensive health of women in the climacteric. Evidence indicates a reduction in polypharmacy, particularly in conditions such as Alzheimer's and osteoporosis, in addition to a significant improvement in functional capacity, flexibility, balance, and motor coordination⁶⁵.

Resistance exercise assumes special relevance in the preservation of muscle mass, counteracting the basal metabolic reduction and adipose accumulation characteristic of this phase. The pathophysiological mechanism involves the secretion of hypothalamic endorphins, with direct action on thermoregulation and the attenuation of vasomotor symptoms, in addition to musculoskeletal strengthening and improved respiratory capacity ^{1,66}.

Exercise plays a crucial role in modulating anthropometric and biochemical parameters, particularly in the conversion of body composition, lipid profile, and prevention of cardiometabolic comorbidities ⁶⁷⁻⁶⁹. Additionally, the mechanical stimulus of resistance exercise promotes an increase in Bone Mineral Density through greater calcium absorption post-exercise, counteracting the 2-3% annual bone loss post-menopause ³³.

Hormonal Therapy: Conventional and Bioidentical Approaches

Conventional Western medicine has conventional Hormone Replacement Therapy (HRT) as its main pharmacological intervention ^{70,71}. However, bioidentical HRT emerges as a promising alternative, using hormones molecularly identical to endogenous ones, potentially minimising adverse effects. This approach reflects a growing trend towards more naturalised therapies, although regulatory gaps and the need for greater scientific evidence persist ^{71,72}.

Research in bioidentical HRT remains in evolution, seeking to optimise formulations and administration routes within a personalised and multidisciplinary perspective ^{73,74}. This orientation converges with the Eastern view by considering individual needs, albeit through Western scientific paradigms.

While the Western approach focuses on specific evidence-based interventions, the traditional Eastern perspective prioritises energy modulation and global organism balance ². Both perspectives, however, recognise the importance of non-pharmacological interventions, particularly physical activity, as a fundamental element in climacteric management.

The convergence between these perspectives suggests the emergence of an integrative model, where Western scientific precision dialogues with the Eastern holistic view, potentialising more comprehensive and personalised care strategies for women's health during the climacteric.

Eastern Perspective

Studies on TCM Treatments for Menopause

Our article searches on digital platforms provided 14 papers that were grouped in Table 1, allowing for a global analysis of the types of TCM approaches to menopause and the responses to symptoms.

Reference	Design	Sample Size	Method	Outcomes
75	Randomised controlled	49 women	Qigong	Significantly improved genital self-image and sexual function.
76	Randomised	125 women	Qigong	Significant reduction in symptoms and improvement in health-related quality of life (HRQoL) in Spanish postmenopausal women.
77	Randomised	125 women	Qigong	Significant improvement in somatic, psychological, and urogenital levels, in the total MRS scores. Also showed improvements in general health, physical fitness, vitality, and mental health according to the SF-36.

78	Randomised	82 women	Acupuncture combined with <i>Ningshen</i>	The combined intervention showed improvements in clinical symptoms and sleep quality. Reduced recurrence rate and proved safer compared to conventional treatment.
79	Randomised	70 women	Auriculotherapy combined with moxibustion	The combination of therapies proved effective in improving sleep quality, anxiety, and depression in perimenopausal women with insomnia.
80	Randomised controlled	82 women	ACE Acupuncture	There was an improvement in the intestinal microbiota with increased adiponectin, resulting in weight loss.
81	Randomised controlled	30 women	Laser Acupuncture, Diet Therapy	There was a significant improvement in metabolic syndrome parameters compared to diet therapy alone.
82	Prospective, randomised, controlled, crossover without washout	32 women	Systemic and Auricular Acupuncture, Meditation (Collective + Guided Individual), Diet Therapy	- Hot Flushes (HFRDIS): Significant improvement of 56.9% ($p < 0.001$). - Quality of Life (MRS): Improvement of 39.9%, but without statistical significance ($p = 0.057$). - Quality of Life (WHQ): Improvement of 14.3%, no significance. - Behaviour Profile: High adherence to acupuncture (83.9%) and collective meditation (80%); reasonable adherence to diet (57.3%) and individual meditation (56.9%).
83	Randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled	60 women	Herbal Medicine (M. Officinalis L.)	M. Officinalis L. contributes to a significant improvement across all domains of quality of life (MENQOL).
84	Randomised controlled	96 women	ACE Acupuncture	Significant reduction in body measurements, abdominal fat, appetite, and inflammation. Improvement in glucose and lipid metabolism.
85	Randomised controlled	13 women	Herbal Medicine – Tianwang Buxin Granule (TWBXG) formula	Significantly reduced PSQI scores.
86	Randomised controlled	60 women	Fire Needle combined with moxibustion	Significantly improved tear secretion, prolonged BUT. Reduced dry eye symptoms and improved systemic symptoms.
87	Cross-sectional	4595 women	Diet Therapy	Daily consumption rich in soy reduces menopausal symptoms in women in Shanghai.
88	Randomised, controlled, double-blind	70 women	Acupuncture	Improvement in sleep and comorbid depression in the short and medium term.

Table 1. Information and characteristics of TCM treatment studies for menopause

The compiled results indicate a consistent and positive effect of various TCM techniques on a wide spectrum of menopausal symptoms. Mind-body interventions, such as *Qigong*, proved particularly effective.

In the scope of instrumental therapies, acupuncture and its variations – including ACE acupuncture and laser, revealed themselves to be versatile in the management of specific comorbidities. Studies by Cai *et al.* ⁷⁸, Feng *et al.* ⁷⁹, and Zhao *et al.* ⁸⁸ demonstrated

that acupuncture, alone or combined with herbal medicine (*Ningshen*) or moxibustion, is effective in reducing sleep disturbances, anxiety, and depression.

Also notable is the evidence of its action on metabolic changes: research by Jin *et al.*⁸⁰, Kamal *et al.*⁸¹, and Yan *et al.*⁸⁴ suggests that acupuncture can induce weight loss, reduce abdominal fat, improve glucose and lipid metabolism, in addition to modulating the intestinal microbiota and inflammation, suggesting an effect that goes beyond symptomatic relief and acts on the pathophysiology of postmenopausal metabolic syndrome.

Despite the promising results, critical analysis highlights important limitations. Methodological heterogeneity is striking, with variations in designs, often small sample sizes (e.g., Yang *et al.*⁸⁵, n=13), and diverse intervention protocols, making it difficult to conduct robust meta-analyses and generalise the results. Comparison between studies is further hindered by the use of different outcome scales (MRS, SF-36, MENQOL, PSQI). Furthermore, most research lacks long-term follow-up, leaving the sustainability of the observed benefits uncertain. Thus, the results must be interpreted with caution, and new standardised and comprehensive clinical trials are essential to consolidate TCM as an evidence-based option.

In summary, the body of reviewed evidence reinforces the premise that TCM offers a multifaceted therapeutic arsenal for the comprehensive care of women during the climacteric. Interventions such as Qigong, acupuncture, herbal medicine, and diet therapy have demonstrated effectiveness in improving vasomotor, psychological, urogenital, and metabolic symptoms, in addition to favouring overall quality of life. The diversity of approaches enables personalised medicine, tailored to the needs of each patient. Future studies with larger samples, prolonged follow-up, and cost-effectiveness analyses are needed to consolidate these practices in clinical guidelines and expand access to a more humanised and holistic approach to menopausal care.

A Focus on Qigong

Qigong, a practice dating back thousands of years and integrated into TCM, represents an Eastern care paradigm focused on health promotion and disease prevention through energetic self-management. Its primary goal is to potentiate, direct, and mobilise *Qi* of the body through gentle, concise, and sequenced movements. This practice synthesises meditation, postural control, breathing techniques, and body movements, aiming at optimising physical health, treating specific pathologies based on prior diagnosis, and promoting a harmonious connection between mind and body^{89,90}.

This care perspective, which emphasises continuous care and self-regulation, is common in community spaces such as parks and gyms, estimated to be practised by over 70 million people in China^{91,92}. From an Eastern physiological standpoint, *Qigong* operates through a vegetative feedback model, unifying the autonomic nervous system and increasing the body's capacity for self-regulation⁹³. This structure is based on three essential pillars: *Qi*, *Shen* (which correlates the mental with the emotional, essential for concentration and focus), and *Jing* (which interconnects with cellular functional capacity and cellular nucleus functions)^{94,95}.

There are two main modalities of *Qigong*: internal and external. Internal *Qigong*, fostered as an autonomous practice, promotes balance and reduces energetic blockages by increasing the flow of *Qi* throughout the body. It is fundamental for health prophylaxis, improving the immune system, regeneration processes, longevity, and spiritual development, demonstrating benefits in terms of physical and emotional well-being⁹⁶. In turn, External *Qigong* constitutes an energetic treatment performed by qualified therapists, following an individualised assessment and diagnosis⁹⁶.

Scientific evidence corroborates the mechanisms underlying these benefits. Studies show that the practice promotes an increase in the flow of *Qi* in the meridians, awakening the perception of energetic flow and sensations of numbness along them. Matos *et al.*⁹² attested to these changes at the capillary level through thermography, finding a significant increase in peripheral microcirculation.

Consequently, the physiological, emotional, and energetic benefits of *Qigong* are vast, including the reduction of blood pressure, depression, and anxiety, and an improvement in balance and lower limb strength^{89,97-99}.

Given this framework, it is essential to adopt a preventive and care perspective, resorting to the regular practice of *Qigong* at the beginning of perimenopause. As Davis⁹⁶ argues, this practice is crucial for delaying hormonal decline, maintaining vitality, and sustaining a balanced emotional state during this transition. The practice should incorporate four fundamental components: gentle movement, strengthening postures, self-healing massage, and meditation. The focus resides in harmonising the body and mind, nourishing the *Yin* and the flow of *Qi*, thus offering a holistic approach to alleviating the myriad of symptoms that characterise this phase of a woman's life.

Self-care Protocol

The protocol begins with a series of light dynamic stretches, aimed at warming up the joints of the cervical region, shoulders, wrists, knees, and ankles.

Subsequently, a basic *Qigong* posture is adopted for the execution of a deep abdominal breathing exercise, called Dantian Breathing. The purpose of this technique is to establish a conscious connection and promote the accumulation of *Qi* in the Lower Dantian region, located approximately three fingers below the navel (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dantian region location (Qihai)¹⁰⁰.

Execution:

1. In the basic posture, a mental connection is established with the aforementioned region.
2. The hands are positioned over the lower abdomen (hypogastrium), with the right hand in direct contact with the body and the left hand superimposed on the right.
3. The tip of the tongue is kept in contact with the upper palate (a posture known as "connecting the Du and Ren meridians") and the feet are firmly in contact with the ground ("rooting").
4. The respiratory cycle is performed deeply and diaphragmatically, coordinated with a gentle contraction of the perineal muscle during the exhalation phase.

Dynamic Exercise – Sipping the Essence of the Bubbling Spring

The main objective of this protocol is to tonify the Kidney energy (including the adrenal glands) and promote hormonal and body fluid regulation, mitigating fatigue. The practice is based on the stimulation of the KID-1 (*Yongquan* – "Bubbling Spring" – Figure 2) acupuncture point, located on the sole of the foot, to absorb Earth *Yin* energy.

Execution:

1. Starting Position: Adopt an erect posture with the feet approximately 90 cm (3 feet) apart and a moderate flexion of the knees.

2. Hand Placement: Position the back of the hands on the lumbar region, over the anatomical area of the kidneys.
3. Preparation and Connection: Perform a few cycles of deep inhalation and exhalation to establish a state of presence. Concentrate on visualising the KID-1 (*Yongquan*) point on both feet, conceptualising it as the portal of entry for telluric (*Yin*) energy into the organism.
4. Respiratory Cycle and Visualisation:
 - Inhalation: Visualise the Earth energy ascending from the feet, through the lower limbs and pelvis, to be stored and nourish the renal and adrenal region.
 - Exhalation: Execute a deep flexion of the knees (squat), keeping the vertebral column relatively straight (simulating sitting in a chair). Avoid lumbar hyperlordosis to prevent vertebral compression and gluteal protrusion.
5. Dynamic Movement:
 - Inhalation: Slowly return to the erect position, conceptualising the ascent of telluric energy to the renal region, under the hands. Applying gentle pressure with the back of the hands against the back can facilitate the sensation of support and energy concentration.
6. Repetitions and Auxiliary Technique: Execute the squat and lift cycle between 9 and 18 times, coordinating exhalation with the descent and inhalation with the ascent. During the inspiratory phase, gently contract the anal sphincter (perineal lift) to concentrate and retain the *Qi* in the renal region, preventing its dissipation.

Figure 2. Kidney point number one location ¹⁰⁰.

Ovary Bridge Massage

This procedure aims to promote the nourishment of the ovaries, relieve congestion in the reproductive organs and associated energy meridians, and aid in the modulation of the hormonal decline characteristic of the climacteric.

Execution:

1. Position yourself in the supine position (on your back) with the soles of the feet in contact (adapted Baddha Konasana position).
2. Elevate the pelvis, transferring the body's weight to the upper dorsal region and the lateral faces of the feet, maintaining support.

3. Isometrically and gently contract the gluteal and pelvic floor musculature.
4. Position the palms of the hands in the lower abdominal quadrant, immediately superior to the inguinal folds.
5. Execute circular massage movements with the palms of the hands, performing approximately sixteen rotations, or until a sensation of warmth is perceived in the abdominal region.
6. Lower the pelvis in a controlled manner and conclude the protocol with a few cycles of deep breathing to promote relaxation.

Frequency Indication: For obtaining benefits, daily practice is recommended, or a minimum of three times a week.

Scalp Massage

This procedure aims to stimulate the points of the Governing Meridian (Du Mai) located on the scalp, with the intention of dissipating tension and promoting the release of negative charge, through a combined technique of massage and conscious breathing.

Execution:

1. Using the fingers, execute a massage technique similar to combing, applying gentle and uniform pressure throughout the scalp, with emphasis on the midline (the path of the Du Mai).
2. During the practice, adopt a state of mental concentration (visualisation) with the aim of dissipating accumulated tension.
3. Synchronise the ritual with a specific respiratory pattern: inhale, directing the intention and the sensation of energy flow towards the vertex (top) of the head; exhale, directing the sensation of release in a caudal direction, towards the cervical region (neck).
4. The cycle of massage and breathing should be repeated sequentially for twelve times.

Scalp massage acts as an effective somatosensory intervention in the improvement of insomnia. The mechanism is based on two main pillars: mechanical stimulation and neurophysiological modulation. The rhythmic pressure of the fingers promotes local vasodilation, increasing blood perfusion and reducing the muscle tone of the epicranial musculature, which is often tense in states of hyperarousal associated with insomnia. Simultaneously, the technique aims to activate the parasympathetic system, through synchronisation with deep diaphragmatic breathing, decreasing the activity of the Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Adrenal (HPA) axis. This modulation promotes a state of psychophysiological relaxation, facilitating the transition to sleep by lowering cortisol levels and regulating circadian rhythms. The visualisation component further aids in interrupting the flow of ruminating thoughts, a common perpetuating factor of insomnia.

Foot Massage

The procedure consists of performing acupressure on the *Yongquan* point. The stimulation of this point promotes the descent of excessive *Yang* and the afflux of *Qi* to the lower region of the body, which facilitates the state of relaxation necessary for the onset of sleep.

Additionally, the physiological relationship between the Kidney and Heart systems is explored. By supporting the Kidney, the Heart is calmed, modulating mental activity and promoting the balance between Water (Kidney) and Fire (Heart), which is fundamental for effective rest.

Heart Healing Sound

The nocturnal practice of the Six Healing Sounds, with emphasis on the Heart sound "Huuu", aims to facilitate the release of accumulated tensions and promote emotional homeostasis, preparing the organism for restful sleep. Its execution acts upon the functional sphere of the Heart (*Shen*), being indicated for disorders of anxiety, insomnia, mental agitation, and stress.

Execution:

1. In the Basic *Qigong* Posture, start with the hands positioned on the lower abdomen, palms facing upwards.
2. Inhalation: Maintain stillness.
3. Exhalation: Lift the hands to the height of the heart, keeping the arms in an oval shape.
4. Rotate the palms outwards, moving them away until they are near the temples (thumbs close to the temporal points), with the gaze directed upwards.
5. Rotate the palms inwards, directing them towards the eyes (a few centimetres away), conceptualising the projection of calming *Qi*. Close the eyes briefly to potentiate relaxation.
6. Lower the hands back to the height of the heart, reopening the eyes and maintaining a distance of one fist from the torso.
7. Inhalation: Rotate the palms downwards, with the fingers almost touching, and gently push the hands towards the abdomen, concluding the cycle.

The complete sequence should be repeated six times, after which a period of rest in *Dantian* breathing is recommended to integrate the effects. The emission of the guttural sound "huuh" (phonetics similar to "hook" without the final consonant closure) should be vibratory, felt in the throat, to maximise resonance and the regulating effect on the cardiac system.

5. Final remarks

The analysis undertaken successfully achieved the objectives of this work, evidencing the significant potential of TCM in the care and management of women during the menopausal period.

The structured review of 14 experimental studies demonstrated that a multifaceted TCM therapeutic arsenal, including Acupuncture, *Qigong*, Herbal Medicine, and Diet Therapy, offers clinically significant efficacy in addressing the core symptoms that compromise quality of life. Specifically, TCM interventions were shown to be effective in managing vasomotor symptoms (hot flushes), psychological changes (insomnia, anxiety, depression), urogenital atrophy, and, crucially, modulating cardiometabolic risk factors (weight, lipid, and glucose metabolism) associated with postmenopausal hypoestrogenism.

3.4. TCM vs. Conventional Care: A Paradigm Shift

The comparison between Eastern (TCM) and Western conventional care perspectives revealed a key point of convergence in the recognition of non-pharmacological interventions (such as physical activity/*Qigong*) as fundamental to climacteric health. However, TCM distinguishes itself through its holistic, personalised, and syndromic approach. While Western Medicine focuses on hormone replacement to address ovarian failure, TCM targets the systemic re-equilibration of *Yin-Yang* and the preservation of *Jing*, offering a strategy that is adaptable to the unique manifestation of symptoms in each patient (e.g., Kidney *Yin* Deficiency vs. Spleen/Kidney *Yang* Deficiency).

3.5. Future Directions and Clinical Integration

This study confirms the viability of TCM as a valuable complementary or alternative resource to the conventional medical model. To fully integrate these practices into mainstream clinical guidelines, future research must overcome the observed methodological limitations. Standardised clinical trials with larger sample sizes, long-term follow-up, and comprehensive analyses of cost-effectiveness are essential.

Ultimately, embracing an integrative model of care combining the quantitative precision of modern Western diagnostics with the time-tested principles of TCM's energy and essence regulation is paramount to promoting a humanised, personalised, and sustainable quality of life for women throughout the entire climacteric spectrum.

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